

ETHNOMEDICINAL STUDY IN DYANGANGA WILDLIFE SANCTUARY OF BULDHANA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study entitled *Ethnomedicinal study in Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary of Buldhana District* was carried out with the aim to identify the medicinal plants. During study 76 distinct ethnomedicinal plant species were found belonging to 63 genera and 37 families. Among the observed families, the family Fabaceae has the largest number (10 spp.) of species (13.15%), followed by Apocynaceae, Caesalpiniaceae, Moraceae, and Rutaceae (4 spp.) each (5.26%), followed by Anacardiaceae, Combretaceae, Lamiaceae, Poaceae and Verbenaceae of (3 spp.) each (3.94%). It was come to know that the tribal people have unique knowledge to cure as many as 32 diseases, in which leaf is the main plant part used to treat human ailments. There were 51 (67.10%) tree species, and 12 (15.80%) species of herbs were highly used in therapeutic purpose than 10 (13.15%) species of shrubs and 3 (3.95%) species of climbers. The most often used plant parts were is leaf which contributes up to 33.33 % followed by fruit contributing 17.78% of total plant part and bark contributes 16.30 % of the plant part used to treat various health ailments. Herbal remedies are prepared using fresh materials form 26 species (34.22%), while 10 species (13.15%) were used in dried form and 40 species (52.63%) local people either in fresh or dried form to treat various ailments. Most herbal medicine was administered in the form of crushing 34 (25.18%) followed by powder 32 (23.71%) and decoction 27 (20%), mentioned by the local people.

Keywords: Ethnomedicine, wildlife sanctuary, indigenous knowledge, traditional medicines, Informant Consensus Factor (ICF)

Introduction

India has one of the highest floristic diversities on the planet, making it a genuine emporium of fragrant and medicinal plants. Approximately 35,000 to 70,000 plant species have reportedly been utilized for medical purposes worldwide at some point in history by various cultures. Tribal communities in India provides a list of the country's most important medicinal plants. Knowing that a certain plant was utilized by traditional healers in the past to cure various ailments has led to the discovery of numerous effective herbal medications (Ekka and Dixit, 2007). Drug residues lead to the growth of difficult to treat drug resistant microorganisms, and people are searching for safer herbal substitutes (Nisha, 2008).

Particularly in developing nations, where it is thought that extensive use of plants with therapeutic effect does not result in intoxication, medicinal plants are significant for public health (Jagtap *et al.*, 2020). Majority of population of India are rural based. The rural and tribal communities reside all over the Indian territory. Among these there are 47 tribal communities resides in Maharashtra. The Dyanganga Wildlife

Sanctuary in Buldhana District has potential source of medicinal plants. The area has considerable number of primitive people having traditional knowledge about the medicinal plants. The present study was attempted to collect and document the ethnic valuable information about the ethnomedicinal plant used by the local people.

Materials and Methods

Extensive field surveys of the Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary were conducted. Later, Vaidas, Mukhiya, and other villagers provide compilations of ethnomedicinal knowledge. Local residents from the local and tribal areas were interviewed to compile the statistics. The Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary is surrounded by Botha, Chichkhed Bund, Mandi and Matargaon villages (**Figure 1**). These villages were selected for the ethnomedicinal data collection based on the availability of traditional healers, elders, and knowledgeable persons. The ethnomedicinal data were gathered with the help of 135 informants from these villages. Field observations and group discussions, semi-structured interviews using the techniques described by Martin (1995) and Cotton (1996) were used to gather ethnomedicinal data.

Figure 1. Map of Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary

Result and Discussion

The present study has documented 76 various ethnomedicinal plant species and their therapeutic applications in the Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary (Table 1). There were 63 genera and 37 families which represented the species. Among 37 plant families, Fabaceae has the largest number of species used to treat various human ailments (13.15%), followed by Apocynaceae, Caesalpiniaceae, Moraceae, and Rutaceae (5.26%) and Anacardiaceae, Combretaceae, Lamiaceae, Poaceae and Verbenaceae (3.94%) with 10, 4 and 3 plant species respectively (Table. 2) As per the distribution of medicinal plant of Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary is concerned out of 76 plant species 29 species (38.1%) were found to be naturally occurring in agriculture

field, followed by 18 (23.7%) species in protected area, 17 (22.4%) species found in transition zone and 12 (15.8%) species found in buffer zone (Table 3. and Fig. 1)

The plant parts used for the medicine preparation were leaf, fruits, flower, bark, gum, seed and whole plants were utilized by the indigenous communities. The most often plant part was used is leaf 45 (33.33 %) followed by fruit 24 (17.78%), bark 22 (16.30 %), stem 10 (7.4%) seed 8 (5.93%) and whole plant 8 (5.93%), flower 7 (5.2%), root 6 (4.44%), gum 5 (3.7%) to treat various health ailments (Table 4).

The present paper insights a brief account of the uses of various ethnomedicinal plants parts used against the disease like diabetes,

fever, jaundice stomach problems, skin diseases, wounds, cough, cold, diarrhoea and dysentery by the people of Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary region. The highest number of 29 plants species were used to treat diarrhoea and dysentery, 22 plant species were used to treat skin disease, 11 plant species were used to treat diabetes, 9 plant species were used to treat stomach problems and 5 plant species were used to for treatment of jaundice. ICF was calculated to look into the level of homogeneity among the informants for the medicinal plants used to treat human ailments. The study shows ICF values ranging from 0.54

to 1 (Balinado and Caunca 2021). ICF value was found higher in fever (87.27%) whereas the lowest value was found in diarrhoea and dysentery (54.09%) (Table 5). Herbal remedies are prepared using fresh materials form 26 species (34.22%), while 10 species (13.15%) were used in dried form and 40 species (52.63%) by local people either in fresh or dried form to treat various ailments (Table 6). In the present study, most of herbal medicine was administered in the form of crushing 34 (25.18%) followed by powder 32 (23.71%) and decoction 27 (20%), mentioned by the local people. (Table 7)

Fig. 1 Source of Medicinal Plants

Conclusion

The knowledge on the use of indigenous plant species has a variety of ethnomedical uses. Unfortunately, because most of the ancient customs and culture are oral, the majority of India's traditional ethno-botanical knowledge is eroding more quickly every day. Organizations, government agencies, ethno-botanists, and the pharmaceutical industry must work together to collect, preserve, and uphold this knowledge. In order to meet the goal, both domestically and internationally, efforts should be made to document and computerize beneficial medicinal plants and their traditional use. The Dyanganga Wildlife Sanctuary has been reported medicinal plant species of potential uses. However, to ensure the preservation of these therapeutic plants, it is crucial to put the appropriate conservation practises into place.

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Table 1: Medicinal Plants used to treat various Human Ailments

Scientific Name	Family	Local Name	Habit	Plant parts used	Condition of Preparation	Application	Route of Administration	Citation
<i>Abelmoschus manihot</i>	Malvaceae	Aibika	Sh	Sd, B	D	Stomach and intestinal disorders, cut and wounds	Seeds are dried & crushed and a tonic is made to cure ailments. A paste of bark is used to treat cut and wounds	<i>Jain et. al 2011</i>
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Fabaceae	Babool	T	Gm, Rt	F/D	Used to treat teeth ache and diarrhoea	Gum is used on wound healing, dysentery. Root tonic is used against cancer and liver problems	<i>Agrawal et al., 2010</i>
<i>Acacia catechu</i>	Fabaceae	Khair/Katha	T	L, Hw	F/D	Digestive problems, sore throat and ulcers	Heartwood extract is used to cure sore throats, ulcers and skin ulcerations. Decoction of leaves is used to treat digestive problems.	<i>Yadav et al., 2019</i>
<i>Acacia leucophloea</i>	Fabaceae	Hiwar	T	B, L	F/D	Gastrointestinal	Leaf juice mixed with cow milk is used to cure bleeding piles	<i>Feo et al., 2011</i>
<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	Simaroubaceae	Maharukh	T	L, B	F/D	Wounds, Body Swells & Skin rashes	Paste of leaves is made to cure skin problems.	<i>Mishra et al. 2007</i>
<i>Albizia lebbek L.</i>	Fabaceae	Sirish	T	Gm, L	F/D	Toothache and Skin disease	Gum is to cure toothache. Leaf paste is applied on skin diseases	<i>Ghani et al., 2010</i>
<i>Aloe barbadensis Mill.</i>	Liliaceae	Korphad	H	L	F	Skin diseases and burns	Leaf flesh is used for skin problems and is used as a moisturizing agent.	<i>Kaur et al., 2024</i>
<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Rutaceae	Bael	T	L, Fr	F/D	Stomach problem, dysentery, diabetes	Fresh leaves are taken orally for the stomach problem Fruit extract taken with sugar	<i>Thirumal et al., 2023</i>
<i>Annona reticulata L.</i>	Annonaceae	Ramphal	T	Fr	F	Heart health, joint pain and diabetes	Fruit is eaten raw to treat heart related disorders and diabetes.	<i>Pathak et al., 2014</i>
<i>Annona squamosa L.</i>	Annonaceae	Sitaphal	T	Fr	F/D	Stomach aches	Fruit is consumed to treat stomach disorders	<i>Kumar et al., 2021</i>
<i>Aralia racemosa</i>	Araliaceae	Jatashankar	Sh	L	F	Common cold, asthma, diarrhoea and haemorrhoids, liver damage	Leave extract is used to treat liver damage	<i>Rao et al., 2017</i>
<i>Argyrea speciosa L.</i>	Convolvulaceae	Vidhara Vel	Clmr	L	F	Joint health, skin health and boosts vitality, and cure boils and swellings	Leaf extract is used to from tonic which severs to skin health and boost vitality and cure boils and swellings.	<i>Galani et al., 2010</i>

<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Liliaceae	Shatawari/ Marbat	Sh	Rt	F/D	Sexual stimulant, digestive problems and infertility	Root powder is taken with sugar to boosts sexual health in males and females	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Neem	T	L	F/D	Indigestion, acidity and skin disease.	Leaves are added in hot bathing water to prevent skin diseases.	Nagini <i>et al.</i> , 2005
<i>Bauhinia variegata L.</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Kachnar/Kanchan	T	L	F/D	Diabetes	Leaves are used to treat diabetes.	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Bombax ceiba L.</i>	Malvaceae	Katsawar/ Saur	T	B, Rt	F/D	Skin disease and menstrual problems, treat a cold or cough	Bark extract powder is used to treat acne and pimples. Root powder+ black pepper+ ginger powder	Gupta <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Bombusa bamboo</i>	Poaceae	Bamboo	T	St, L	F	Stomach disorders, ringworms	Decoction of leaves is used to treat stomach disorders, diarrhoea and intestinal worms.	Tomar 2019
<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Buresraceae	Salai	T	L, B	F/D	Headache	Crushed leaves are applied on head overnight.	Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Buchnanania lanzan Spreng</i>	Anacardiaceae	Charoli/ Char	T	L, Rt	F/D	Diarrhoea.	Root and leaf powder mixed with buttermilk to treat diarrhoea.	Banerjee <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Palas	T	Fl, L	F/D	Hypertension and liver	Flower and leaf extract helps to treat hypertension and improves hearth and liver health.	Jhade <i>et al.</i> , 2009
<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i>	Fabaceae	Sagargota/ Fever Nut	Sh	L,	D	Cardiovascular disorders	Decoction of leaves is done to treat cardiovascular disorders.	Sasidharan <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Apocynaceae	Rui	Sh	L, Lt	F	Rheumatism, skin disorders	Warm leaves are tied to legs to cure rheumatism. The mixture of latex and turmeric applied on the skin disorders.	Meena <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Apocynaceae	Rui	Sh	Rt	F/D	Skin diseases and snake bites	The milky latex is used to treat cancer and acts an antidote to cure snake bites.	Pophale <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Carissa congesta</i>	Apocynaceae	Karvand	Sh	Fr, Rt	F	Stomach ache, diarrhoea	Fruit juice is useful cardi tonic. Decoction of root is used to treat stomach ache, diarrhoea	Bhosle <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Cassia fistula L.</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Bahawa/ Amaltash	T	L, Fr	F/D	Ring worm, Skin disorders,	Fresh leaves are used for ring worms and skin diseases.	Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2017
<i>Cassia tora L.</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	Tarota	H	Sd	F/D	Skin disease	Paste of seed powder is used on skin.	Verma <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	Casuarinaceae	Khadsherni or Saru	T	Fr, B, Rt	F/D	Acne, stomach dental problems	Bark decoction is also useful for treating abdominal pain. Root is helpful to maintain oral hygiene by chewing on the roots on a regular basis.	Tiwari <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i>	Rutaceae	Limbu	T	L, Fr	F/D	Aid digestion, and scurvy	Fresh fruits are consumed to maintain good gut health and treat scurvy.	Jain <i>et al.</i> , 2020

							The dried epicarp of fruit and leaf powder is used to treat skin disorders.	
<i>Chloroxylon sweitenia</i>	Rutaceae	Bhera/ Bhirrha	T	L, B	F/D	Wound healing, cough and cold	Leaf paste is used externally to treat deep cuts, wounds and fungal infection on skin Bark decoction is used to treat cough and cold and used to treat bruises and painful joints	Charanraj <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	Cuscutaceae	Amarbel	Clmr	Wp	F/D	Diabetes	Consuming 5gm of amarbel seed powder helps to lower blood sugar levels.	Khan & Widunbilu 2021
<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Poaceae	Gavti chai	H	L	F	Headache, cough and cold	Leaf tea is used as a sedative for the central nervous system.	Shah <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>Cymbopogon martini</i>	Poaceae	Tikhadi	H	L	F	Hair growth, skin disorders	Leaf oil is applied on hair to promote hair growth. Leaf oil is applied on the skin to treat skin disorders.	Promila, 2018
<i>Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.</i>	Fabaceae	Shisam	T	L	F/D	Jaundice	10-15 ml juice (leaves) taken thrice in a day helps in eliminating pus in urine and in treating jaundice	Sudhakar <i>et al.</i> , 2013
<i>Datura metal L.</i>	Solanaceae	Dhotra	H	L, Sd	F/D	Wound healing, asthma	Seed paste is directly applied on wounds. Dried leaves are smoked for treating asthma.	Monira <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	Ebenaceae	Tendu	T	L, F	F/D	Diarrhoea, jaundice, stomach disorders	Decoction of bark is used to treat diarrhoea, jaundice by tribal communities. Fruit is used to cure stomach disorders	Shinde <i>et al.</i> , 2024
<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i>	Bignoniaceae	Medshing	T	L	F	Acidity	Decoction of leaves is used to cure acidity	Joshi <i>et al.</i> , 2016
<i>Embilica officinalis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Aawla	T	Fr, L	F/D	Diabetes, diarrhoea, hair and eye health	Fruit is consumed to cure diarrhoea and diabetes and improve eye sight.	Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2022
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	Myrtaceae	Nilgiri	T	L	F	Cold, fever and cough	The paste of fresh leaves is boiled, helps to clear nasal congestions and cure cough and cold	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Ficus racemose L.</i>	Moraceae	Umber	T	Fr, B	D	Gum ache, stomach ache and diarrhoea	Bark powder is used to treat gum aches. Fruits are directly used orally for stomach ache	Awasthi <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Ficus bengalansis L.</i>	Moraceae	Wad	T	Fr, L	F	Digestive disorders, wounds and swellings	Fruit consumed directly improve digestion. Latex extracted from the bark can be applied to wounds and swellings.	Gopukumar <i>et al.</i> , 2015

<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Lamiaceae	Shivan	T	Fr	F	Dysentery	Ripped fruit juice with sugar and pomegranate juice taken orally to cure dysentery	Arora <i>et al.</i> , 2017
<i>Grewia tallifolia</i>	Tiliaceae	Dhaman	T	B	F	Ulcer and wound healing	Bark powder is applied on wounds externally. Bark powder is used to treat mouth ulcers	Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2022
<i>Haldina cordifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Haldu	T	B, L	F/D	Skin diseases, wounds, liver disorders.	The paste of leaf is made and applied on the wounds. Decoction of leaves, bark is used to cure liver disorders, skin disorders.	Muthupandiyan S <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>Hardwickia binata</i>	Fabaceae	Anjan	T	L	F	Diarrhoea	Paste of leaf is made and taken orally with water to treat diarrhoea.	Shingade <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Kalanchoe pinnata Lam.</i>	Crasulaceae	Panphuti	H	L	F	Acne, diarrhoea and blood dysentery	Leaf juice is applied on skin acne. The juice from fresh leaves is used to treat diarrhoea, blood dysentery	Rajshekhhar <i>et al.</i> , 2016
<i>Lantana camera L.</i>	Verbenaceae	Ghaneri	H	L, Rt	F	Ulcers, asthma, swelling, skin disorders	Leaf extract is used to treat ulcers, cancer, asthma, ulcer, swelling. The powdered root in milk given to children for stomach ache.	Rao <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Largerstroemia speciosa</i>	Lythraceae	Jarul/ Taman	T	L	F/D	Diabetes, fever, stomach problems	Decoction of leaves is traditionally used to treat fever, treat diabetes and help the body use insulin more efficiently.	Rautmale <i>et al.</i> , 2024
<i>Lawsonia inermis L.</i>	Lythraceae	Mehendi	Sh	L, Sd B	F/D	Skin diseases, jaundice and dysentery.	Leaf paste is used to treat skin diseases. Powdered seed mixed with ghee is effective against dysentery. Decoction of bark is used to jaundice	Lote <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Limonia acidissima L</i>	Rutaceae	Kavith/ Kauth	T	L, Fr	F/D	Diarrhoea and dysentery, sore throats	Leaf juice is used to treat indigestions and dysentery. The unripe fruit can treat gum disease, sore throat, diarrhoea.	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Mahua	T	Fl	D	Sexual impotency	Powder of flower is mixed with milk and taken to overcome sexual impotency.	Devi <i>et al.</i> , 2016
<i>Mangifera indica L.</i>	Anacardiceae	Aamba	T	B	F/D	Alzheimer's disease, diabetes, jaundice and kidney stone	Decoction of bark is used to make tonic to treat jaundice. Fruit is consumed for dissolution of kidney stone.	Parmar <i>et al.</i> , 2010
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Mimosaceae	Lajlu	H	L	F	Ulcers, diabetes inflammations, asthma	Fresh leaves are used to make a tea that helps to reduce blood sugar levels, reduce anxiety as well as depression and also treat stomach ulcer	Mali <i>et al.</i> , 2022

<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Shevga	T	L, Sd	F/D	Gum ache, wound, healing, stomach ache, diabetes	Seed and leaf powder is used to treat wounds and stomach problems. Leaf extract is used in diet to maintain blood sugar levels.	Pareek <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Mytragyna parviflora</i>	Rubiaceae	Kadamb	T	L, B	F	Ulcers, wound healing	Leaf paste is used to treat wound healings and ulcers. Bark decoction is made used to cure	Choudhary <i>et al.</i> , 2016
<i>Ocimum Americanum L.</i>	Lamiaceae	Dev tulsi	H	L	F	Skin disease	A paste of leaves is applied on skin or on an infection	Mahendran <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Ocimum basilicum L.</i>	Lamiaceae	Kali tulsi	H	L,Sd	F	Cough, cold, sore throat, skin disease, rashes and diabetes	Decoction of leaves added in honey or tea to cure sore throat, cough and cold Leaf paste is applied on skin to treat rashes Seeds are taken orally which reduces the blood sugar levels	Mahendran <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Ougeinia oojeinensis</i>	Fabaceae	Tewas	T	B,	F/D	Cuts and wounds	A paste of bark is applied topically to cuts and wounds	Samyal <i>et al.</i> , 2013
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Bhui Awla	H	L, Wp	F	Jaundice, diabetes, and intestinal infections.	Leaf extract is taken orally to cure jaundice. Tonic from whole plant is made to cure liver, diabetes intestinal problem	Bekoe <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Pongamia pinnata L.</i>	Fabaceae	Karanj/ Kojab	T	Sd B	F/D	Skin ailments, piles,	Seed extract is used to treat bronchitis. Decoction of bark is used internally for bleeding piles	Yadav <i>et al.</i> , 2010
<i>Ricinus communis L.</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Erandi	T	L, Sd	F/D	Constipation, Swellings	Leaf oil extract is used in labour pain before and after the child birth. Seed oil is taken orally to cure constipation and bloating of stomach.	Chouhan <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Rauwolfia serpentina L.</i>	Apocynaceae	Sarpagandha	Sh	Rt	D	Insomnia	Root powder mixed with butter for insomnia	Kaur <i>et al.</i> , 2017
<i>Sapindus indicus L.</i>	Sapindaceae	Ritha	T	Sd	D	Hair growth	Seeds extract used in shampoos to promote hair growth.	Ghanshyam <i>et al.</i> , 2024
<i>Semicarpus anacardium L.</i>	Anacardiaceae	Biba	T	Sd Fr	F/D	Chronic rheumatic disorders	The combination, <i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> , <i>Terminalia chebula</i> , seeds powders with jaggery, has excellent results in chronic rheumatic disorders	Raut <i>et al.</i> , 2007
<i>Schleichera oleosa</i>	Sapindaceae	Kusum	T	Fr	F	Hair growth, indigestion	Repined fruits are consumed orally to cure indigestion	Karthikeyan <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Syzigium cumini</i>	Myrtaceae	Jambhul	T	B	D	Diabetes, indigestion, jaundice	Bark juice with buttermilk is used to treat constipation, whereas an intake in the morning has been claimed to stop blood in stools.	Swami <i>et al.</i> , 2012

<i>Tectona grandis L.</i>	Verbenaceae	Saag	T	L	D	Indigestion, diarrhoea and dysentery	Decoction of bark is used to treat digestive disorders like diarrhoea and dysentery	Goswami <i>et al.</i> , 2009
<i>Tamarindus indica L.</i>	Caesalpinaceae	Chinch	T	L, B	F/D	Digestive problems	Dry powdered of bark is given on the digestion problem or other gastric pain	Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2024
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Combretaceae	Arjun	T	B	D	Health tonic, Cardiovascular problems	Decoction of dry bark is taken orally for the febrifuge as a natural coolant and cardiac stimulant	Palaniappan <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<i>Terminalia belirica Roxb.</i>	Combretaceae	Behda	T	St, Fr	D	Indigestion	Fruit is used a Triphala Churna to cure indigestion and gastric problems.	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Hirda	Tr	L	F	Sore throat, ulcers, diabetes and constipation	Decoction of leaves is used as mouth gargle in oral ulcers and sore throat. Leaf powder is used to cure constipation.	Bhattacharyya <i>et al.</i> , 2013
<i>Tinospora cardifolia</i>	Menispermaceae	Gulvel	Clmr	St	F	Constipation, joint pain	Stem powder mixed in milk help elderly person with join pain and constipation problem.	Mittal <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>Tridax procumbens L.</i>	Asteraceae	Kambar modi	H	L	F	Wound healing	Leaves are crushed applied on wounds.	Beck <i>et al.</i> , 2018
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Verbenaceae	Nirgudi	T	L	F/D	Headache, skin problems, liver disease.	Dry Leaves are smoked to cure headache. Leaves are crushed and mixed with wheat flour to cure skin diseases.	Venkateswarlu <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Zizyphus jujuba Mill.</i>	Rhamnaceae	Ber	T	B, Rt	F/D	indigestion, dysentery	Powdered bark is mixed with honey and milk to cure indigestion, dysentery,	Agrawal <i>et al.</i> , 2023

(H=Herb, Sh= Shrub, T=Tree, Clmr =Climber, St= Stem, B= Bark, Hw =Heartwood L = Leaves, Rt= Root, Sd= Seed, Fr= Fruit, Fl= Flower, Fb= Flower Bud, Gm= Gum, Wp= Whole Plant, Lt=latex, F= Fresh, D= Dried, F/D= Fresh/ Dried)

Table 2: Most occurring families found in wildlife sanctuary and their plant part used to make herbal medicine.

Family	No. of Species	Habit				Plant part used
		Herb	Shrub	Tree	Climber	
Fabaceae	10	-	1	9	-	Seeds, Frutis, Leaf and Bark
Apocynaceae	4	-	4	-	-	Leaf and Flowers
Caesalpinaceae	4	1	-	3	-	Leaf, Bark and Gum
Moraceae	4	-	1	3	-	Leaf, Bark, Gum and Fruit
Rutaceae	4	-	-	4	-	Leaf, Fruit, bark and Gum
Anacardiaceae	3	-	-	3	-	Seed, leaf and Gum
Combretaceae	3	-	-	3	-	Leaf
Lamiaceae	3	2	-	1	-	Leaf
Poaceae	3	2	-	1	-	Leaf
Verbenaceae	3	1	-	2	-	Leaf and Bark

Table 3: Source of Medicinal Plants

Source	Number of Species	Percentage (%)
Naturally occurring in Agriculture Field	29	38.1
Protected Area	18	23.7
Buffer Zone	12	15.8
Transition Zone	17	22.4
Total	76	100

Table 4: Plant part used as traditional medicine

Plant parts	Total responses	Percentage (%)
Leaf	45	33.33
Fruit	24	17.78
Seed	8	5.93
Root	6	4.44
Latex /Gum	5	3.7
Flower	7	5.2
Bark	22	16.30
Stem	10	7.4
Other (Whole plant, Oil)	8	5.93
Total	135	100

Table 5: Types of disease for informant consensus

Category of Disease	Number of species	Number of informants cited	ICF	% of ICF
Cough & Cold	17	67	0.7575	75.75
Diarrhoea & dysentery	29	62	0.5409	54.09
Diabetes	11	52	0.8039	80.39
Fever	8	56	0.8727	87.27
Jaundice	5	27	0.8461	84.61
Stomach problems	9	55	0.8518	85.18
Skin disease	22	69	0.6911	69.11
Wounds	11	58	0.8245	82.45

Table 6: Nature of preparation of herbal medicines

Nature of preparation	Number of species	Percentage (%)
Fresh	26	34.22
Dried	10	13.15
Fresh/Dried	40	52.63
Total	76	100

Table 7: Methods of preparation of traditional medicines.

Forms of preparation	Total response	Percentage (%)
Chewing	5	3.71
Crushing	34	25.18
Decoction	27	20.00
Extract	15	11.11
Juice	15	11.11
Powder	32	23.71
Other (Whole Plant)	7	5.18
Total	135	100